

GROUPS AND THEIR EFFECTS IN ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

The human is a social being and survives as the part of a group in every field of life from the birth. Group is a community consisting of one or more individuals who interact with each other in order to accomplish a certain goal. The groups are created formally and informally within the organization at different times and for different goals. Those groups have the negative and positive influences on the organization structure and function. In this work, the group concept in the organizations is studied and the influence of group behaviors within the organizations is discussed conceptually.

Keywords: Groups, Group Behavior, Group Dynamic, Informal Groups, Formal Groups

Introduction

Since the humans are the species living in groups, they must communicate, cooperate and interact with each other in order to survive. This cooperation and interaction occur within the formal and informal groups in the community.

As a result of works focusing on the emotions of human and work group, not on the efficiency principle in the organizations; the emotions, which are not considered in the factions, small groups and rational models, are mostly discussed. In this approach, called "Human Relations", the Official Organization and its relations with the environment were neglected. Formal organization was considered as a system determining the economic structure only on the paper and the (informal) social organization in the enterprise has begun to become primary research subject.

It is started to consider the transactor as a group member whom his/her behavior is determined widely with the group norms and group values, not an independent individual. It is understood that the transactor doesn't always act according to the rules determined by the business management and "Homo Economicus" logic, so to speak, acts based on the logic restricted with his/her "emotions" (Reitz, 1977).

Group Concept

The term, group, used in the daily language, defines "to become plural" in the most general sense. We use the group term for two or more individuals who come together and interact with each other in order to accomplish a certain goal. The group concept is defined diversely in the social psychology and sociology. According to those definitions, the conditions such as joint norms, joint goals and feeling themselves as a group are suggested in order that the crowd becomes a group (Monique & Michael, 2015).

There are many definitions related to the group concept from past to today. The group, consisting of more than one individual, brings up that it is a social being. As in one of the definitions of group, it is stated that the creation of group arises from the perception which the individuals feel themselves as the members of a group, it is mentioned in another definition that the individuals should be together for the purpose of accomplishing the certain functions in order to form a group, the group members should mutually fulfill the liabilities which they assume, and the norms should be developed within the group. At the same time, the group is also defined as a social fact which consists of the individuals who develop the norm and behaviors and interact with each other through the power of communication (Koçel, 2011).

The groups are the factors having the physical and social orders with the constructive and unifying features same as the individuals. They struggle same as the individuals in order to survive and to protect their existence. They take the steps against the risks which are unavoidable for every living being such as separation, disintegration and disappearance, and furthermore, make an effort to grow and develop by using the environmental opportunities with their own possibilities.

However, just as being in the living beings and individuals; if there are any problems and risks which they cannot overcome with or they believe that they cannot solve their problems with their own powers and possibilities, then the uneasiness, instability and disturbances may also occur within the group. At the end, the group may separate, disintegrate, unify or merge with other groups or may entirely disintegrate and disappear. Thus, we may describe the group which is not different than any human regarding

the living features as the small or big communities that interact with each other, are aware of the existence of each other psychologically and perceive themselves as the group (Schermerhorn, Osborn, Bien, & Hunt , 2012).

In another definition, the group is stated as an individual community which is in interrelation with each other regularly and has the common values or norms regulating their behaviors in the various status or role (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2012).

There should be the common problems, issues or goals in order to interact with each other. Group work requires some features allowing the groups to meet and organize. Those are the group leadership, authority, role, communication and socio-metric structures. The joint norms of the group members play the unifying and moral increasing roles having the ideologies. Beside this, it may be wrong to say that the group features are same as its members. The features of a group are different than the individual features of members which form it. This fact may partly be explained with the synergy concept. Synergy means that the entirety may be different than the pieces forming it. As an example for this concept which is frequently used in the physical sciences; the combined effect (synergy effect), occurred through taking two drugs together, is clearly different than the effect which may occur upon taking them separately (Hunter, Thorpe, Brown, & Bailey, 2009).

So, we may say that each group has a personality specific to it and this personality is completely different than the personalities of individuals forming it. In this regard, as the groups and the individuals forming them are examined, this feature, called “Social Synergy”, should also be considered. The concept of group means the mutual interaction of two or more individuals in order to accomplish a certain goal. The primary reasons of forming the group by the individuals and of the group behaviors are that the individuals have confidence in and esteem themselves, take share from the achievement, and think that this is their fault in case of failure (Judge & Stephen, 2013).

We face with many different group types within the organization. Those are Formal, Informal, Task and Control Group Types, Interest and Friendship Groups. When we briefly describe the subject (Judge & Stephen, 2013);

- **Formal Group** means that the group is formed by the organization and the limits of subject, which the group will discuss, are determined.
- **Informal Group** means the groups that are formed in order to meet the social needs and their goals are not determined.
- **Control Group** means the group which is under the responsibility of a manager and the individuals account before the manager only. The example is the manager, responsible for the financial affairs department, and his/her staff working under his/her responsibility.

- **Task Group** means the group which is formed in order to perform the tasks that are determined by the organization. In order to accomplish the goal, the group may have the cross-control relations. If the crime is committed or there is a fault in the institution, then other units should also work in coordination with each other.
- **Interest Group** means the group formed by the individuals who are interested in the certain subjects.
- **Friendship Group** means the group which is formed by the individuals who become close to each other, are interest in the same subjects, and find the many lowest common denominators.

Reasons of Becoming the Member of A Group

As well as the groups formed with the sense of mission, there are groups which are formed randomly. All individuals in the society are the members of a group somewhat. The individual already becomes the member of a group instinctively once he/she is born; so, the individual already begins to act with the sense of some responsibilities which the society that he/she takes place needs. As the individual gets away from the sense of loneliness upon becoming the member of a group, it helps to him/her to gain his/her self-confidence.

The achievements, gained collectively by the group members, add many values to the group members such as recognition, recognition socially, obtaining the certain statutes. In this regard, the individual lives as the member of certain groups by the effects of certain belief, attitude and norms from the birth. The real reason of which the individual would like to be the member of a group is that he/she feels intimacy to that group and has the several common characteristics with individual's belief (Eren, Örgütsel Davranış ve Yönetim Psikolojisi, 2010).

General Features of Groups

In order to organize the groups, the features of group leadership, authority, communication, socio-metric structure should be available. It is important to know those features in order to analyze the reasons of group behaviors. The leaders, who know those features, may manage the group productively. T.R. Mitchell and R.Steers studied the group factors with a model, and examined the personal, situational and group structure characteristics. They discussed the group structure and processes in the work. The subjects such as group norms, role and statute relations, observance behavior that are the features of group structure are discussed in detail in the below chapters. The group processes consist of the processes of group-in and group-out communication, conflict, decision-making and leadership. The brief descriptions of those processes are provided below: (Ayalp, 2013).

- **Group Processes Stage:** Carrying out all intergroup activities is provided via communication. The individuals obtain the in-group behavior rules and all solution ways through this way.
- **Conflict Stage:** It is a factor which prevents the individual and group activities. Furthermore, the conflict is not always the negativeness, but leads to the certain developments.
- **Decision-making Stage:** It is defined as the group's correct and efficient decision-making process. Shaw (1978) found that the groups were more influenced by the decisions taken by the group than individually and that the ideas, filtered by many individuals, were noticed fast, even if they were faulty and less error was made in his work.
- **Leadership Stage:** The leaders are the representatives of a group, and the individuals who protect the group's interests and provide the group's solidarity and affect the individuals and direct their activities by keeping them together.

General Functions of Group

Psychological, Individual Functions

The role of group is important regarding the meeting of individual's needs in participation of individuals in the groups. When it is discussed in this regard, it may be said that the group satisfies, first, its need (Levi, 2010).

For example, the needs of belonging, in other words, the needs of friendship, support and love are the needs that can be satisfied upon becoming the member of a group. An individual, becoming the member of tennis club, decides to become the member of this group, since he/she likes the people whom he/she meets there or needs to become friend with the new people as well as would like to play tennis. On the other hand, it may also be said that the groups are the means of developing, strengthening or verifying the sense of identity of the individual and of maintaining his/her self-esteem. The individual may develop some emotions regarding who he/she is or may verify it, gain a status and may increase his/her self-esteem through his/her group membership. In the above example, if becoming the member of a tennis club is a status symbol of an individual, then the group performs an important function regarding the satisfaction of such need.

The groups are the means of determining the facts and solving the problems. There are some researches showing that the groups may take the more correct and doughtier decisions than the individuals in solving the problems that they face with. According to the results obtained from those researches, the groups may reach to more correct solutions than the individuals. Occurrence of incorrect ideas in the group fast, noticing the faults faster may be one of the reasons of it. Even if the individual doesn't see his/her fault, then other group members may see it,

The problems are more revised in the groups and thus, they don't make more faults than the individuals. For some individuals, the group is a shelter that he/she takes shelter in order to avoid the risky environment. With this feature, the group becomes a mean which increases the security against a common and powerful enemy or the threat and creates the sense of strength (Levi, 2010).

Formal and Organizational Functions

The formal functions are the functions which are assigned to the group and the group is officially responsible for. The groups have the certain functions related to accomplishing the principle goals in the organizations and the groups operate in this direction and perform some formal functions (Schein, 1978).

Multi-directional or Complex Functions

The groups are the goal in some cases and means in some cases for the individuals. However, the relation or differentiation between the goal and mean, which are the fundamental reasons of participating in the group, may not be accepted sufficiently clear and significant. The group membership, which may be accepted as the mean initially, turns into the goal later. The individual, who participates in the group in order to satisfy his/her need that is not directly related to the group, maintains his/her membership after satisfying his/her need via group.

In addition to this, it should be emphasized that the groups, assuming the formal work, also perform mostly the psychological functions and therefore, turn into a natural group (Robbins & Judge, 2010).

When the individual has right to speak on his/her environment, and feels that he/she is recognized by the others, he/she will be able to get rid of his/her troubles, and recognize the social reality surrounding him/her. The group needs the loyalty of its members in order to function well. The group members always seek the opportunity to participate in the group and to develop during the life of group (Schermerhorn, Osborn, Bien, & Hunt, 2012).

Classification of Groups

The groups may be classified in the various ways. In these classifications, the goals, size, structure of the group and interaction of group members with each other are generally considered.

Formal and Informal Groups

The most common classification forms, used for the groups in the literature, are formal and informal groups. This classification is summarized as follows.

Formal Groups

The formal groups are the groups which are formed in order to accomplish the certain goals that are clearly determined. These groups are formed by an authority, generally except the members in order to perform the certain functions and consciously (Franz, 2012).

Such groups have primarily the following characteristics (Hicks, 1979):

- The task, power and responsibilities of each member are clearly determined and defined,
- The relation between the members are regulated,
- They have a durable and planned structure; since they give importance to the formal, their structure is relatively inflexible,
- The membership is obtained consciously, at a certain time and generally, clearly.

Informal Groups

In general, the members of the groups, which are formed in order to perform the certain tasks formally, form the informal groups developing various relations between them in order to satisfy their individual needs and emotions. If we call the group which attaches to the organization's goal and structure as the formal group, then we may define the informal groups as the less organized, hidden acted groups (Stewart & Manz, 1998).

Since the informal groups have some functions desired by their members, they are born and maintain their existence. One of those functions is to protect and maintain the cultural values which the group adopts. This function helps to maintain the certain living-style and to protect the solidarity and integrity of the group. The second function is to provide the social saturation. Informal organizations deliver the appreciation, status to the individual and possibility to interact with others.

The third function of the informal groups is the communication. The group will develop the communication systems and channels specific to itself in order to satisfy the members' needs and to inform them about the events which may affect them. The fourth function is the social supervision which will influence and regulate the others' behaviors (Fujishin, 2013).

Informal groups may emerge through the simple factors such as location or may be formed due to the factors which are difficult to be

understood such as satisfying the certain needs of some individuals (Robbins & Judge, 2010).

Because the organizations may not satisfy all needs of people with the assigned formal tasks and material possibilities.

Primary and Secondary Groups

According to many behavioral scientists, the most important distinction occurs between the primary and secondary groups. This distinction was, for the first time, developed by a former sociologist, G.H. Cooley (1909) and the emotional behaviors of group members lie behind it (Fujishin, 2013).

Primary Groups

The primary groups are the communities which mostly, the group members know each other, are frequently in face-to-face relation with each other and this relation is maintained uninterruptedly. There are strict, even daily relations and communications between the members. The members know more or less their roles and personal characteristics. The example of this is the family and the civil servants who play the game together and work together in the same department, know each other very well and are in relation every day. As being noticed, the fundamental characteristic of the primary groups is that they are small.

As the mutual solidarity or emotional support may occur densely in these groups, the severe and conscious personal conflicts and schism may also occur. Every human absolutely survives as the member of the primary group. Otherwise, the deprivation from the senses of love and belonging to the group, closeness to the individuals and emotional relations, and from the development of powerful social aspect of the human may be in question (Eren, Yönetim Psikolojisi, 1986).

In fact, the lack of warm attachments, which are the function of the common characteristic of complex industrial community between the people, is suggested as the most powerful source of difficulties between the individuals today (Fujishin, 2013).

For this reason, even though the groups are sometimes the sources of conflict and unhappiness conditionally, the human being will become the member of primary groups in order to avoid deprivation and loneliness (anomie) which we mention. So, the relations may occur between the rooted people and as a result of it, powerful solidarity or severe conflicts may occur in the primary groups (Eren, Yönetim Psikolojisi, 1986).

Secondary Groups

The secondary groups are the groups which are formed on the supreme ideals and targets that the members feel jointly, and the members may not know each other closely, since the group members don't meet each other due to numerous people. So, they are the groups having the very rare communication and interaction atmosphere between the members (Duncan, 1981).

The relations in the secondary groups are mental, rational and contractual. The trend toward not being personal in these relations is dominant. Such groups don't create the satisfaction sense in contrary to the primary groups, but create it indirectly by providing the means that the members will accomplish the aims (Schein, 1978).

The relations of members in such groups are limited. The examples are a university having the numerous students, fellow townsmen residing in a big city, all citizens of a country, and the worker groups registered in a union.

Structure and Dynamic of the Group

The group structure is a quite complicated concept. However, some mechanisms, which generally regulate the mutual relations of group members under the group structure, are studied.

Role and Status Relations

One of the important factors, forming the group structure, is the role and status relations between the group members. The individuals in a social system expect that the other individuals of this system show the certain behaviors. Such expectations related to the behaviors are called "role" (Franz, 2012).

Learning of roles and causing the change in the behavior occur with the certain phases, and as a result of perceiving and explaining (interpreting) of group expectations by the individual for a certain position and selection and realization of the behavior complying with it, the individual completes the real role behavior. If this behavior is different than the group's expectation, then it is notified that this behavior is faulty through a feedback mechanism (Monique & Michael, 2015).

The different roles are expected from the individuals who are within the same group. This is called the role differentiation. If this differentiation is not certain and clear, then the group's efficiency and performance will diminish. However, since the very strict role differentiation leads to which the role of a member within the groups is not assumed by another member, it may also adversely affect the group performance. In some cases, the role differentiation may not correspond to the personality and skill of the

individual. Thus, the individuals may not perform the functions which are expected from them, and as a result, a diminish may occur in the total performance of the group. The individuals play the numerous roles simultaneously. Some of them are the roles which are played while working and out of work. However, those roles may sometimes conflict with each other. This role conflict may occur in the different ways. For example, the perception of other person's role by the different persons in a different manner may cause the conflict. Another type of conflict may occur, in the event that the personal attitude and values are different than the role's requirements. The role conflict causes the negative results both for individual and group. The individual and group performance diminishes and the satisfaction decreases.

Another factor, affecting the group performance, is the vagueness of role. The individual, who doesn't certainly know or doesn't perceive correctly what is expected from him/her or how he/she will do it, is in the vagueness of role. As the role conflict creates an important problem mostly for the lower levels of the organization, the role vagueness is a problem for the higher levels (Schermerhorn, Osborn, Bien, & Hunt , 2012).

Besides the role relations, the status relations of the individuals within the group are also important. In general, the role and status are handled depending on each other, because a role is attached to each status and a status is assigned to each role.

The status is an evaluation that is made by other individuals of the social system about the individuals in that social system (Monique & Michael, 2015).

The group members may have the different status from each other in a group. Having the different status between its members means that the group has a hierarchic structure (Robbins & Judge, 2010).

Group Norms

There are rules which manage the behaviors of members in many groups. So, those directives, showing what are recognized and what are prohibited, are called "Norm".

The group norms are the means which help and regulate to perform the correct activities complying with the group's aims and to increase the achievements (Gray, 1977).

As the norms may be the very simple rules, they may be the complex prohibition series. As the norms tell the members what they should do or not, they also cover the rewards and penalties of the behavior at the same time. The behavioral rules, which are important for the operation of group, are gradually becoming important, as the group or work expands. Some common pathfinder lines are necessary to help the group to reach an aim.

However, as Thibaut and Kelley pointed out, the norm structure may become complicated so as intervening the efficient operation of the group (H.Kelly, 1959).

In such cases, the more attention is paid to strictly observe the rules than performing the functions which the rules should serve primarily. The real or imaginary pressures are generally created by the many observers of social area in order to ensure that the group norms are observed. There is a common opinion that the idea of conformity to norms collides with the personal satisfaction and as a result, achieving the social welfare. In reality, the case may be this, but such superficial explanations disregard the positive and sometimes, necessary aspects of observing the group norms. Those social pressures may provide the stability and information on accomplishing the functional targets of the members individually and entire group.

As much as any norm is adopted by the group members and is distinctive, it is so important and has the pressure power. The powerful group norms decrease their powers on the individual behavior and attitude by influencing the personal values and norms or putting them under the pressure. Even though the individual knows that his/her opinions and behaviors are correct and realistic, sometimes, he/she must say or accept in contrary to the reality in order to avoid conflict the group (Eren, Yönetim Psikolojisi, 1986).

So, we may list the primary characteristics of norms as follows:

- The norms are the collective value judgments which regulate the members' behaviors putting them under the influence and pressure within the group.
- The norms are developed by the majority of group for the behaviors which are recognized by many or all group members as important.
- The norms don't completely remove the personal ideas and emotions of the individual, but put under the social pressure. Therefore, the group norms don't change the personal beliefs and emotions of the members, but the individual's behaviors or in other words, attitudes are affected voluntary or involuntary. So, the group norms are not the representatives of individual desires, wills and beliefs.
- Creation of norms requires the certain time. During such period, some members, especially the group leaders explain some norms and try to have them adopted by the group. The group formalizes the norms as a result of several negotiations and by giving mutual concessions.
- Some norms are not adopted widely by all members. They are called the partial norms or schism or subgroup norms.

Conformity Behavior

Formed group values and norms apply pressure on the individuals' behaviors and thoughts and change their behaviors. "Changing the individual's behaviors in direction of the desires and expectations of all or some part of the group members is called "conformity behavior". In order that the individual changes his/her behaviors, the real or unreal desires and expectations of the group members must be perceived by the individual (Eren, Yönetim Psikolojisi, 1986).

Even though the individual knows that his/her some behaviors are wrong, he/she has to conform to the group's atmosphere, requests and expectations. The individual's behavior changes without change in the personal belief and values here. Even though the individual knows that it is wrong, he/she has an attitude of identifying himself/herself with the group under the group pressure and the group pressure almost controls and directs the individual's behaviors. The individual obeys the group and acts of identifying himself/herself in order to conform to or match the group's idea, almost being afraid of staying out of group and being punished. Here, as the group has an impact on the individual as a pressure factor, it has also an attraction and value. By the course of time, if these attraction and value are maintained, then the individual may adapt his/her beliefs and thoughts entirely to of group. If the conformity behavior of the individual is which he/she believes that the group's thoughts and values are correct, then it is called the adopt behavior.

Group Leadership

As the human is the social living beings, living in groups, they are the beings that require the hierarchic attachment to the leaders and administrators who will manage the groups that they form and bring them to the targets. Directing the human group, directed to the certain aims, to the targets requires the separate skill and persuasive ability. In that case, we may define the leadership as the total of knowledge and skills of gathering a group of people around the certain aims and of motivating them to accomplish those aims. As the human is the social living beings, living in groups, they are the beings that require the hierarchic attachment to the leaders and administrators who will manage the groups that they form and bring them to the targets.

It is known that the individuals, carrying out the activities within the formal organizations, act as if they are the members of informal groups at the same time. They may be considered as the groups which are formed naturally or by themselves. Furthermore, it is also known that the informal groups have a certain status system and the most efficient and kingpin

member gains the title of “natural leader” with them from the researches of Hawthorne to today (Dereli, 1976).

Natural leader plays the wide and important role to determine the group’s objectives and may change those objectives within the certain limits.

One may say that the leader is the person who determines the objectives of group which he involves in, and most efficiently directs the group in order to achieve such objectives (Daft, 1997).

The qualities of a good leader are listed in general as authority, knowledge, team work ability, achievement desire and resolution, acting fair and being balanced (Schermerhorn, Osborn, Bien, & Hunt , 2012).

Group Dynamic

The small groups have existed from such time when the first human family has been formed and the philosophy and generalization had been made about them at the ancient times. For example, Aristophanes in *Lysistrata*, 400 B.C., wrote a drama discussing the solidarity and disintegration within a group. With this, the people began to examine the functional processes of small groups scientifically very recently (Davis, 1979).

In particular, the studies on small groups started from 1920s, and its importance was recognized with the Group Dynamics Theory of Kurt Lewin (Schermerhorn, Osborn, Bien, & Hunt , 2012).

As Nietzsche mentioned, “*Madness is an exemption for the individuals but a rule for the groups*”, the group behaviors’ fundamentals are formed by suggesting the sometime insane and sometime genius ideas by the individuals who gather for a certain aim and by recognizing the achievement and failure as the result of their efforts (Judge & Stephen, 2013).

The minimum requirement necessary that the community becomes a group is “interaction” and accordingly, the group means "more than one person who interacts". Thus, each member influences the group with the group’s norm, value, behavior and characteristics. The mutual interaction process brings us to the concept of "dynamic".

In the small groups, the social process that the people are in face-to-face relation with each other is called the group dynamic. The word "dynamic" is sourced from Greek, meaning power (force); therefore, the group dynamic means the studying of powers within the group (Davis, 1979).

More clearly, the concept of group dynamic means the effects of changes in any part of the group on and reactions of them in the group members and group structure. As the group dynamic discusses the influences and reactions between the individuals within the group, it also covers the

dependency of group on the external conditions as a unit and the relations of it with another group (Eren, Yönetim Psikolojisi, 1986).

Here, dependency of the group on the external groups as a unit and the relations of it with the other groups are important as much as the influences and reactions between the individuals. The common point of all researches related to the group-individual relations is to give importance to the individual. However, since the individual is discussed within the group and in interaction with the group, not individually, those researches are the “Social Psychological” characteristics in essence. The minimum requirement necessary that the community becomes a group is “interaction” and accordingly, the group means "more than one person who interacts". Thus, each member influences the group with the group's norm, value, behavior and characteristics. The mutual interaction process brings us to the concept of "dynamic". In this part, the "group dynamic" covers the group's influences and occurrence of those influences with which processes.

The term, Group Dynamic generally reminds the cause and effect relations within the group, forming the groups and their functions. In general, the researches and theoretical approaches addressing to the group and individual relations are categorized under three groups.

The works related to the norm development within the group and conformity of individual to this norm, the researches which examine the relation of individual's attitude change with the group and analyze the group as a power that causes the individual's attitude change or prevents this, and the researches which examine the group's impact on the individual's productivity comparing the group's work production with the individual's work production.

Effects of Groups within the Organization

Normative Effect of Group on the Individual

Considering the group's internal structure, we know that there are status (position) differences between the members in all groups. The “conformity behavior” to the group norm was mostly observed in the persons at the medium level who suppose that they are recognized “partially” among the bottom, medium, and upper status levels. Those members obtained the support of group up to the certain level, but their situation is not fixed. Fixing the group support absolutely or being rejected depends on them. For this reason, those members attach to the group norms in the most sincere manner and show the conformity behavior to the norms with the great eagerness. Since they know that they are regarded with disfavor by the group, the group losses its attraction for the members in the lowest status to the certain degree. Therefore, they show generally lesser conformity behavior to the group than the members in the medium status who find the group attractive and spend

effort to move to the higher ranks. The leader, who is loved and recognized by the group, has the feeling of confidence; it means that he/she gains the status as high as he/she can obtain, doesn't need to observe the norms very strictly in order to obtain the higher status. In this regard, he/she feels freer than the member in the medium status. Dittes and Kelley suggested in their research that the members at the bottom level don't value the group, but nevertheless, they show some conformity behavior in the observing manner in order to not being dismissed from the group. Here, the question, "Why does the individual want to maintain his/her membership in the group which he/she doesn't value?" may be asked.

In order to answer to this question, we may use the concept of "Comparison Level" developed by Thibaut and Kelley (Thibaut, 1959).

According to those views, the value of group for a member is the difference between the advantage (reward) that it provides to him/her and its cost. The individual has some expectations from the group which he/she is the member. Those expectations are at the certain level. If the group is beyond this "comparison" (expectation) level, it is attractive for the individual. If not, it is not attractive.

Impact of Group on the Change of Individual Attitude

The group may increase or decrease or prevent the change of attitude in its members, namely if this change of attitude is in the group's norm, then the group plays an increasing role in this change, but if it conflicts with the group norm, then the group plays the preventive role in this change of attitude.

This is the result of which the agreement in the group plays the supportive role in order to protect the individual's attitude in direction of the group norm. The group decision is taken as a result of group discussion and the members find an agreement (norm) in the group.

Impact of Group on the Individual's Productivity

During the analyses carried out on the group, it is mentioned that the individual does more than what he/she does by himself/herself within the group.

This fact was observed from the first experimental researches executed with the groups and called "Social Acceleration" by Allport (Thibaut, 1959).

It is very interesting to obtain the similar results from some researches executed in the animals. For example, Chen observed by himself that the ants in the trio groups dig the most sand in the paired and trio ant groups. The common finding in all these similar researches is that the individual works more in the group than when he/she is alone. However,

some researches show that "learning" is slower within the group. For example, Allport observed that the amount of work, carried out in a group, increased, but the quality decreased. Furthermore, other researches, executed in the different times, also showed the group's adverse impact. Namely, being in a group sometimes increases and sometimes decreases the individual's productivity. We may interpret it as follows. The existence of other persons increases the motivation and activity level of the individual. Thus, the possibility of giving the (dominant) reactions, which the individual tends to do, increases. So, if the individual tends to do wrong, then the faults of individual will increase within the group, but if he/she tends to do correct, then the possibility of doing correct will increase. The executed researches show that being within a group increases the individual's motivation. It is considered the contest within the group and sense of being evaluated by others as the source of it. By these feelings, the "Social Acceleration" occurs.

Impact of Groups on the Decision-Making Process

The group decisions were taken more deliberately than the personal decisions until 1960s. It is proved with the executed researches that the groups begin to pass the risky decisions in the later years. The reason of it is that even if the wrong decisions are taken by the group, their risk is shared by the group members with the equal responsibilities. As the individual acts more deliberately and controlled while he/she is alone, he/she is affected by the group's thoughts in the decisions passed by the group.

According to another view, suggesting the different opinions by the individuals in the group causes the discussion of different ideas and adoption and acceptance of such ideas which initially seem strange by the group members. His/her idea is important for each individual; in this regard, the group decisions are taken in the idea denominator closest to the group depending on the moral, ethic, norm and rules. According to another view, the group in the decision-making process tends toward the convincing ideas. The different decisions or ideas are proportionate to the individual's ability to convince the group members.

Impact of Group on the Performance (Social Acceleration)

The experiments on the animals showed the acceleration of individual's behaviors within the group. The fact, which we call social acceleration, is that the individual is affected by the existence of other individuals, carries out the work faster and has the performance. The behaviors of individuals allow for occurrence of what we know with others. When we examine the influence of it on the people, feeling of the existence of others by the individual, especially knowing by the individual that he/she is followed stimulates the individual personally and this is reflected

positively or negatively to the individual's behaviors. In an experiment, the words are given to the subjects and some of those words are repeated frequently and some less. The subjects easily learnt the words which they repeated frequently, and could not learn others. Existence of audiences increased the individuals' estimations and made them accelerated. The similar results are obtained in many of these and similar experiments.

The findings were evaluated through the research and the works were carried out involving many different views on influencing of individuals by the existence of others and why they are stimulated by them. In some researches, as it is suggested that the individual's performance increases with the existence of other individuals, and this is obtained via stimulation, other researches mention that existence of others decreases the performance for personal work and the wrong work is carried out. The researches on social acceleration did not obtain the consistent results yet. The reason is that there are variables in many subjects (Tevrüz, 2012).

Negative Results of Group Membership

Even though the groups provide some advantages and benefits to their members, they may have some banning and pressures on the group members. Since the individual must observe some principles and ideals due to the group membership, he/she must regulate his/her actions and behaviors and change them based on the group's desires and requirements. For example, the limited production issue is the decreasing of norm and standard by a worker satisfying the group's requirement without any personal reason. This fact occurs as a result of group restriction and pressure.

It is not easy and even possible to satisfy all group members. Each decision, taken by the group, is interpreted in favor of the members. Therefore, the individuals seem that they are satisfied with the decisions even which are not in their favor and even require to give personal concession. Thus, it occurs the tendencies toward observing the group's principles and standards unconsciously. However, despite of all these negative results, the individuals need to enter into and become a member of the group (Eren, Yönetim Psikolojisi, 1986).

Impact of Informal Groups on the Formal Groups

The structure, formed during the organizing function, is the informal organization. As the formal organization is formed, the persons, having the qualifications that the work requires, are assigned by the organizer to the determined structure. The theoretical assumption of this assigning is that the persons within the organization will establish the regular relations with each other. In other words, the organizational network and communication network will be the same. However, the groups, which the employees form

between themselves in the organization, and informal organization, formed by these groups, may significantly affect the operation of formal organization.

Group and Personal Health

Nowadays, it is not possible to think the person alone in the organizations. Workers will adapt their behaviors to the organization's rules, but may not act independently from the rules of group which they involve in.

It is not true to discuss the person-group relation only from the point of formal or informal rules that regulate the behaviors. According to the Modern Psychological findings, the individual, conflicting with the group, is sick. As this sickness may be the mental disorder, it may also be the behavioral, emotional and thought disorders. It is not sufficient that the individual becomes a certain group in order to be healthy. In other words, unless the worker becomes the full member of any group in the organization, he/she will not reach to the psycho-social peace (Homans, 1971).

Group and Personal Behavior

It is thought frequently that informal groups and organizations conflict with the principles of formal organization. For this reason, it is not desired the forming of new groups, except the organizational structures of organizations.

However, one should remember that as the informal organizations prevent the works in the formal organization, they also positively contribute to such works. It is natural that the informal organizations have the rules slowing down the works as well as accelerating them. In this case, what the administrator must do is to regulate the relations between the formal organization and informal organization in direction of the organization's aims (Erdoğan, 1991).

It is not true to accept that the worker's behaviors are limited with the rules of formal organization under the today's social conditions. The interesting situation, which the modern human faces with, is as follows: If an individual established the relation with other persons and groups in the organization, he/she has the opportunity to control the political, economical and social power threatening his/her personality (Fujishin, 2013).

For this reason, the workers look for the ideal colleague group as well as the benefits provided by the organization, and expects some characteristics in this ideal colleague group. As these and similar results show, it is not true to think the workers independent from the groups or as only the members of formal groups.

Structure Change of Formal Organization

The organizational structure of the organization will be formed at the end of organizing works. Thus, in-organization formal groups will be formed, the administrators of those groups will be assigned, and the relations between the groups will be determined. At the end of such work, the organization charts, which we may call the structural chart of the organization, will occur. Informal groups will occur within the formal organizations and an organizational relation, which the informal groups establish, will be in question. As the informal organizations are not formed by the organizers, those organizations don't have the structural charts (organization charts) that may be drawn easily as being in the formal organizations. As the foundation objectives of these organizations, which are informal and not conform to the certain schematic forms, are different, the source of rules and value judgments that will be valid in the inter-personal relations will be based on the different parameters. It is an indisputable truth the existence of informal organizations which may not be schematized easily within the formal organization that is schematized with the organization charts, and even if they are schematized, then they change their structures frequently. We may call such organizations as the ameba type organizations which don't have the schematic characteristic; even if they have the schematic structure, then they change the structure frequently, and form the formal organizations during the structural changes again.

Such organizations, having the ameba characteristic, will be formed as a result of inter-personal interactions; the sizes of ameba organization will expand or shrink depending on the significance of social variable which provides the interaction.

Figure 1. Formal Organization Structure Change

If an individual established the relation with other persons and groups in the organization, he/she has the opportunity to control the political, economical and social power threatening his/her personality. If there are differences between the rules and aims of those organizations which have the shapeless characteristic and of the formal organization, then those two

organizational structures will start to affect each other. As it is known that the control is excessive on the members of informal organizations, the informal organizations will be more efficient. Such result will prevent the obtaining of desired efficiency from the formal organizations.

As shown in the Figure 1, let's assume that the formal organization of an enterprise is as the schema that is shown with the straight lines. B, C, D depend on A regarding the relation. There are subordinates depending on each of them. As the some workers suggest that if they expect the softer administrative attitude while dissatisfied from the attitude of administration against the workers in this organization, then C and D administrative attitudes are normal and they may not manage the workers with softer method, B shows softer behavior against the workers and may be disagree with the other senior managers and the workers are aware of this case. In such case, some workers will resist against the administrative attitude, and will select B as their leader in their relation with the administration and will form the informal organization (ameba type, shapeless) which is shown with dash lines in the figure. Occurrence of such organization will significantly affect the efficiency of formal organization.

Organization will have a theoretical structure, and the validity of determined structure will diminish. Such result will cause that the administrators start to reform the formal organizations, and in other words, it will be compulsory to make some changes in the constitutional characteristics of the formal organizations as a result of the effect of informal organizations (Erdoğan, 1991).

Conclusion

The small work groups in the industry are mostly called "informal groups". There is not any position which may be assigned officially to them within the administration mechanism of organization.

We may obtain the following results from the observations during the work life of people and from the behaviors related to this aspect of their lives (Dereli, 1976).

1. If the individuals are close to each other during the work, then they always tend to form some groups in order to protect and support their advantages. The employer doesn't change anything against the existence of such groups. If there are conditions to make the existence of those groups materially possible, then they will absolutely be formed and will maintain themselves.
2. Those groups may fully adopt the objectives of principle organization which they involve in (such as reaching to the higher productivity level). In this case, they play an active role on achieving the said objectives.

3. Those groups may act fully in contrary to and so as preventing the achieving of such objectives of principle organization which they involve in.

4. Those groups may be impartial against the objectives of principle organization; in other words, they are not interested in them. For example, the matter, which the group members of football team of a bank, is only the efficiency in the football field, and they are not interested in the productivity of banking works as a team.

5. The actions such as isolating some individuals and subjecting them to the special treatment or isolating individually or subjecting them only to the special treatment without isolating encourage the social groups which have the very strong internal bonds and sanctions specific to it to be developed fast.

6. Jointly feeling of some simple advantages, which are easily sensed, in other words, easily understood encourages the development of some informal groups which have the strong internal bonds and are beneficial to the members.

7. Existence of a group of natural group leaders within the group increases the achievement possibility of that group.

8. As the groups select their natural leaders, they prefer the individuals who act best fit to the service achieving their objectives.

9. In the cases where the production level is controlled widely with the social means (not having the mechanical rhythm), if it benefits from the ideas, abilities and motivations forming the spiritual value sources which the informal group members have within the organization, then it is possible to increase the productivity so as attracting the attention.

Having such structure by the industrial organizations, forming such groups, creates a potential which must be discussed. When this potential is not used as required, as it may cause the unexpected results, when it is correctly discussed and evaluated, it is possible to obtain the incredibly positive results regarding the increasing of productivity. It is not possible to destroy such groups in the organizations, because formation of such groups is beyond the management's will and control. In the experimental researches, it is found that in case of the individuals work without forming the group, they are very unproductive. For this reason, what the managers must do is to find the way of benefiting from the group fact (Davis, 1979).

In this case, the task of management is;

- To adopt and understand the informal organization,
- To consider the possible influence of any activity which it designs on the informal organization,
- To try to integrate the interests of informal organization with the interests of formal organization as much as possible,

- To prevent in general that the formal works disturb unnecessarily the informal organization.
- The attention should be paid to which informal systems will have the secondary role with the formal systems; otherwise, the employer's objectives, which are protected from the past, may lose in the labyrinth of the small group's interests.
- If the formal system weakens so as preventing the carrying of a work, the informal organization will tend to strengthen in order to fill the authority gap and to keep the group together. In some groups, one may frequently hear, "despite of our observer, we may do some here".
- As long as the informal systems support the organizational targets, the productivity will be obtained at the acceptable level in such system, but this system may easily tend toward the undermining, free-riding or anti-administration attitudes.
- When the administration is weak, it may take such tendencies under the control. This issue will not be solved, when the administration tries to become powerful and autocratic in order to assimilate the informal organizations. Under such circumstances, the informal systems become stronger in order to protect the group and to maintain the work life at the acceptable level. As a result of it, only the negative effects and minimum productivity are seen.

The best composition of the formal and informal organizations is the formation of informal systems which will maintain the group attachment and team work with the primarily dominant formal system in order to protect the objective integrity. In other words, the informal organization should be strong in order to be supportive, but should not be so strong as ruling on the formal organization (Davis, 1979).

In this case, it is necessary to shape the organization again, but as the organization relations are regulated, the psycho-social aspect of the human behaviors will not be disregarded, and the informal structures will not be formalized around the organization's objectives. So, he/she should be the person who is modern organizer, and maintains the differences between two frontiers of organizational structure at the minimum level.

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